

Trans(n/l)ation: The Nation in Translation in the Soviet Books in Bengali for Children and Adolescents

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Abstract: In this article, we are going to study the cultural import of the Soviet books in Bengali translation meant for children and adolescents/young adults, using a selection of such books as type studies. While we shall investigate the structures of indoctrination which are at work in these texts, we shall also explore the patterns of delight they offered for the readers. It can be generally agreed upon that these books worked as ideological state apparatus (ISA). But we shall see that that the ideology they propagated was not merely that of the communist party, but more importantly, these books propagated and instilled a sense of *Russia*: the country, the culture and the people. They were giving birth to a general Russophilia. This was a project of trans(n/l)ation, a project of translating the values of the Russian nation. Russia was to act as the concrete manifestation of socialist idea, as the substance of social change and image of the ideal future which the children were to imbibe. Other soviet cultural texts (from other republics) which got translated into Bengali were always transmitted through the medium of Russian, and were also modelled on the Soviet Russian formulaic structures for children's books.

Keywords: Soviet Children's and Adolescents' Literature, Fairy Tales, Folk Tales, Soviet Books in Bengali, Children, Russian Culture, Bengal and Russia, Communist Party, Russian Nationalism, Bengali language and Russian language, Bengalis and Russians, Soviet Union, Progress, Raduga, Mir, Vostok, Manisha, National Book Agency, Arun Som, Noni Bhowmik, Socialist Realism, Spontaneity and Consciousness, Soviet Nostalgia, Soviet-Era Books.

Literature produced for children and adolescents are meant to delight them, but they are also supposed to condition them, socialise them, and introduce them to the world that they would grow up in. Tacitly (story books) or directly (primers), such texts are tools of various ideological systems to inculcate certain values among the young minds, to instruct them into patterns of thinking during their formative years, and make them ready to receive the knowledge, discipline and human skills which the adult community finds useful and rewarding. In addition to all the features of children's books, adolescent

fictions introduce a certain coming of age narrative that very often involves adventure, frequently introducing adult motifs like love, crisis and war. Keeping this in view, we proceed to study the case of Soviet children's (and adolescents') literature in Bengali translation. As we shall study the structural and ideological aspects of the reception of these books by the Bengali speaking readership, we shall see that these books tempt the young minds into a general fondness for Soviet Union and a left-leaning worldview. But in this article we shall also see that the ideology of Soviet Union was not just communistic, it was deeply rooted in the traditional Russian nationalistic values. Such literature, therefore, did not merely offer a simple communist orientation; going beyond that, they fostered a Slavophilia/Russophilia.

কুশদের বুদ্ধির তারিক করতে হয়। তাদের পর্যবেক্ষণ শক্তি আছে।
 একদা মিশনারীরা এদেশে অকাজরে বিনামূল্যে লক্ষ লক্ষ বাইবেল বিতরণ
 করেছিলেন। খ্রী বলে সেগুলো লোকে পড়ত না। তখন মিশনারীরা বাইবেল
 বিতরণ একদম বন্ধ করে দিলেন। ফলে আজ যদি আপনি বাইবেল পড়তে চান,
 তবে গাঁট থেকে অন্ততঃ টাকা দশেক না খসালে একখানা ভালো বাইবেল পাবেন
 না। কাজেই অবস্থা পূর্ববৎ—বাইবেল এখনো কেউ পড়ে না।
 রাশানরা দিল্লীর বাজারে ছেড়েছে এস্তার মার্কস, লেনিন, স্টালিন, লের্মেণ্টফ
 চেখফ, কিন্তু একদম খ্রী নয়, আবার ছায়া মূল্য থেকে অনেক সস্তা। দেড় টাকায়
 লের্মেণ্টফ পেরে যাচ্ছেন—ভালো কাগজ উত্তম ছাপা। আপনাকে ঠেকায় কে ?
 এবং যেহেতু কাঁচা পয়সা ফেলে তেল কিনেছেন তখন সে তেল আজ না হোক
 কাল মাখবেনই।
 এ সব বইয়ের চাপে পড়ে মার্কিন মুল্লকের সস্তা কেতাব ছাড়া ইংরিজি আর
 কোনো কেতাব আমার বাড়ির সামনের স্টলে পাওয়া যাচ্ছে না। স্টলওলা বললে,
 রাশায় ছাপা ইংরিজি বই বিক্রী করলে কমিশনও নাকি বেশী পাওয়া যায়।
 আমার শুধু দুঃখ রাশানরা যত না মার্কস-এঙ্গেলস্ লেনিন-স্টালিন ছাড়ছে
 তার শতাব্দের এক অংশও টলস্টয়, পুসকিন, দস্তায়ক্‌স্কি, তুর্গেনিয়েফ
 দিচ্ছে না।

Fig. 1: Mujtaba Ali on Soviet books in 1951/52. Probably the first mention of these books. *Collected Works Vol. 11* p 249.

Syed Mujtaba Ali in his *Rai Pithoura's Column* that he used to write in the *Anandabazar Patrika* during 1951-52 probably made the first mention of arrival of Soviet books, which came from a mainstream Bengali littérateur. He notes how the cheap price generates a great appeal among readers, and has practically ousted all other books except cheap American paperbacks. These are not children's books, but we shall still deal with his account in details as that will be helpful for us in understanding the context and mechanism of the circulation of Soviet books for children. In the absence of any full-

fledged study of Soviet Children's stories and fictions in Bengali, we shall draw freely from the general observations about Soviet books and culture made by critics, which will be followed by specific case studies of Soviet children's books, where we shall investigate the applicability of these critical paradigms to the Bengali translations.

Fig.2 & 3: Covers of Bengali translations of works of Lenin and Lermontov

Mujtaba Ali detects the ideological motive, and contrasts the Russian approach with Christian missionary activity of dispensing free Bibles. The missionaries failed to make people read Bible because people did not care for free books. And when they stopped giving it away for free, and decided on a steep price for the Bible, people did not read it either, because the price acted as a deterrent. Mujtaba Ali observes that the Russians have kept the price sufficiently low so that people can be tempted to buy these books, but they are not giving those books away for free or too low a price, which would have resulted in devaluation. Further, Soviet publications fetched greater commission compared to books imported from the west, as the bookseller in Delhi confirmed to Mujtaba Ali, who was stationed in Delhi during that period.

While most books are political tracts of Marx, Lenin and Stalin (and Stalin was still alive), some classics are also available, Mujtaba reports, though he complains that the ratio would be like 100:1, i.e. for every hundred political and ideological tracts there will be a nineteenth century Russian classic realist text on sale. He observes that a work by Lermontov is available at a price of Rs 1.50 which is tempting enough, given the superior quality of print, paper and binding.

Some very useful points can be extracted from this brief reportage of Mujtaba Ali, though he is talking of Soviet books in English language, not in Bengali, and not particularly for children. Probably Bengali books did not appear in the Indian market yet, but very soon they would arrive and conquer successive generations of Bengali readers through the next four decades. Mujtaba's feedback makes it abundantly clear that the Soviet marketing strategy was well planned, and it worked well. Without going through the details of the understanding between the Nehru Government and Soviet Union during this period, one cannot pinpoint the intricacies of the mechanism of circulation of Soviet books in India. But given that P C Joshi, who was the erstwhile general secretary of CPI (1935-47) and later expelled from the party in 1949, known for his closeness to Nehru, was rehabilitated in into the party in 1951, we can assume that the Indian government might have been friendly to Soviet Union in the import of these books, as Joshi's reinstated status in the party suggestively coincides with the mass arrival of Soviet books in India.

An interview of Arun Som, the noted translator of Soviet books into Bengali, that was taken by the present author (which is published in this issue) confirms that initially, the majority of the Soviet books were political and ideological in nature, and classics constituted a minor portion of the total amount of books sent from Soviet Union. But gradually the emphasis on Russian nineteenth and early twentieth century literary classics and children's literature was made, which culminated in the establishment of Raduga in 1982, specialising in those texts. In Russian Raduga meant rainbow. The publishing house was probably meant to be an acknowledgement of other colours which were not red, but existed in a spotless harmony with red, justifying a common whole. Raduga stood for the ability of forging a consensus, thereby establishing hegemony. Rainbow is associated with colourfulness, and a suggestion of inclusiveness is there.

We can thus observe the three different phases of transmission of Soviet books in India: 1. Books are in English, and mostly political tracts, with very few classics. No mention of children's literature (1951-52). 2. Books begin to get translated into Bengali. Children's books arrive on the scene. The earliest specimen that I have been able to trace belongs to 1954 (Fig4&5). This book was printed and published from Kolkata, under some arrangement with Foreign Language Publishing House, Moscow. 3. Progress Publishers (established in 1931), hitherto engaged with political publications, ventures into children's books and nineteenth century Russian classics (the exact year of this change is

not known). Progress operates from 21 Zubovsky Boulevard, Moscow. The Foreign Language Publishing House, operating out of 17, Zobovsky Boulevard is probably merged with Progress, because the Foreign Language Publishing House is no longer heard of from the 1970s. Raduga is set up in 1982 for exclusive publication of classics and children's literature.

॥ মস্কো ও লেনিনগ্রাদ হইতে 'গোশ্বেভার্ডভেমোইয়ে ইজ্‌দাতেল্‌স্তভো দেত্‌স্কোই লিতেরাতুরী মিনিস্তের্‌ভা প্রস্‌ভেস্‌চেনিয়া র.স.ফ.স.র' কর্তৃক প্রকাশিত ও ম. বিলস্কি কর্তৃক সম্পাদিত "উক্রাইনস্কিয়ে নারদনিত্তে স্কাজ্‌কি" (১৯৫৪) হইতে নির্ধারিত চারটি গল্প ॥

॥ মূল রূপ হইতে অমুবাদ করিয়াছেন ॥

শ্রীহীরেন্দ্রনাথ সায়্যাল

॥ মূলের সহিত মিলাইয়া অমুবাদ সম্পাদনা করিয়াছেন ॥

শ্রীঅর্কেন্দু গোস্বামী

॥ প্রচ্ছদপট ও ভিতরের ছবিগুলির মধ্যে পাঁচটি মূল রূপ গ্রন্থে প্রকাশিত ছবির প্রতিলিপি

॥ চিত্রশিল্পী ॥

এ. রচিত

॥ মুদ্রাকর ॥

এস. দে

হিন্দ প্যেপার প্রিন্টার্স

৭৯৯ শোয়ার সাকুলার রোড

কলিকাতা-১৪

॥ প্রকাশক ॥

ইস্টার্ন ট্রেডিং কোম্পানীর পক্ষে

শ্রীদেবীপ্রসাদ মুখোপাধ্যায়

৬৪-এ ধর্মতলা ষ্ট্রিট

কলিকাতা-১৩

॥ অফসেট প্রেট ইস্টার্ন ট্রেডিং কোম্পানীর নিজস্ব প্রেসেস ডিপার্টমেন্টে প্রস্তুত ॥

॥ প্রচ্ছদপট ও ভিতরের ছবি 'ফেটাপ্রিন্ট ৩০' অফসেট মেশিনে ছাপা ॥

সাইজ—১১×৯ ইঞ্চি. ২৪ পৃষ্ঠা। ১৮ পয়েন্ট টাইপ। প্রথম সংস্করণ, ১৯৫৪—৫০০০

মূল্য—এক টাকা

সর্বস্ব সংরক্ষিত

Fig. 4 & 5: Probably the first Soviet Children's book in Bengali, *Ukrainiyo Upokotha*, printed and published from Kolkata in 1954. Front cover and copyright page.

Soviet fictions were earmarked by a planned system of ISA, and Katerina Clark's *The Soviet Novel: History as Ritual* minutely discusses the different aspects, evolutions and expressions of that ideological universe, and while doing that, she draws a significant thread of continuity from the pre-Soviet past which comes to characterise the continuing literary and cultural tradition of the Russian nation. Authoritarianism and government interventions in the Soviet literary world have Tsarist precedents (many would argue that contemporary Russia of Vladimir Putin continues within the same tradition of authoritarianism, though its literary output may be minimal).

Soviet-era authoritarianism is in many respects a continuation of the Tsarist practice, in spite of the massive epistemic break caused by the rise of the communist party. Clark is quick to note:

Ideology is no stranger to the Russian novel in any of its manifestations. ... ideology plays a particular historical role in the relationship between literature and the government. This relationship is very different in the Soviet period from what it was under the tsars, although much of the difference is one of degree only; for several nineteenth century writers – Goncharov, for example – worked as censors, Dostoevsky was close to the tsar's advisor Pobedonostsev, and in the 1830s the infamous Bulgarin worked as a worked as a government agent. Thus, during the old regime there were writers who shared the official ideology, and the government itself played a monitoring role in nineteenth-century literature. (252)

While charting the specific developments within Soviet fiction, Clark cautions us against the adoption of “Western highbrow literary criteria in studying a literature that was not intended to meet them,” and as she begins her study of the trajectory of Russian literature under the Soviets, she insists that “there has always been a distinction between modern Russian and other Western literature, and this distinction became exacerbated under the Soviets” (xi).

While speaking of the distinct continuity of the Russian nation, one cannot miss the obvious sense of perpetuity when the Soviet-era anthem is retained today as the contemporary Russian national anthem, with some appropriate changes of lyric: for example the phrase “Lenin's party strength of the people” (Partiya Lenina Sila Narodnaya) turns into “popular wisdom of our forebears” (Predkami Dannaya Mudrost Narodnaya).¹ But the tune is exactly the same and many parts of the lyric remain unchanged. This is a small fact, but it can assume paramount significance as we propose to consider the essence of the Russian nation that is propagated in the Soviet fictions. Russian literary conventions under the Bolsheviks exhibit an underlying sense of continuity in the midst of all drastic upheavals. We need to acknowledge that nations have no timeless essence, nor they are static. They change significantly, and they also remain the same to an extent. In case of the trajectory of the Soviet books, every new development within the cultural sphere takes into account the tradition of the Russian people, because that tradition provides substance to the cultural structure, as communist ideology gives shape to it. Even that ideology seems to have formed a remarkable continuum with Russian tradition.

Fig. 6: *Dadur Dostana*, a 1955 collection of folk tales for children published by Foreign Language's Literature Publishing House, Moscow. It was probably the first Soviet book for children in Bengali that was imported from Soviet Union. Folk tales are a unique repository of traditional wisdom and they offered the perpetual values of Russia.

Anatomical similarity has been suggested between socialist realism and Russian tradition: “The Socialist Realist novel forms a tradition that rests on canonical exemplars. Consequently, medievalists who study the conventions of hagiography and other such texts tied to a canon will find much in common between the distinctive features of their texts and those of the Soviet novel” (Clark xii).

The underlying mythical structure of Soviet books is another case in point, which asserts this continuity of the Russian nation. Secular myths of the great revolution, the great patriotic war, the giant leap forward, the path to communism were celebrated in the Soviet books, as we shall presently observe in our case studies and type studies in this article. As Socialist realism was gradually giving way to newer forms of writings during the 1970s and 1980s and the grip of communist ideology was slackening, it was observed that Socialist realist paradigms were seamlessly functioning as “Christian Realist, Nationalist Realist, or as some version of Spiritual Realism” (Clark 270). Clark does not mention whether such books were still officially published during the 1970s and 1980s, but in all likelihood, they were not, prior to Gorbachev's arrival on the scene. This is another example of continuity, which might deceptively appear as a paradigm shift. Socialist realism is characterised by the Russian practice that calls for a ideological rearrangement of reality (realism in the West was also a bourgeois doctrinal rearrangement of reality, but it was soon supplanted by various literary movements from Romanticism onwards which went beyond reality altogether).

Fig 7: Illustrated Children's tale of a hat that apparently came alive because of the kitten underneath

The myths of the Russian nation come to represent a higher form of reality, somewhat in the vein of Plato's divine reality. Socialist realism accommodated the dominant myths of the time and portrayed reality in the light of those mythical paradigms. Clark makes a categorisation of a three-level reality in Socialist Realism: The people at the ground level, the ordinary mortals, form a shadow world. The Kremlin forms the higher world, and above that structure stand the supra-terrestrial beings, Lenin

and Stalin who constitute the topmost form of reality (142). However, Clark's vertical division of levels of reality can be faulty. Clark does not realise here that the reality of the people on the ground may not necessarily be that of mere shadow within socialist realism. Instead, the politicised depiction of the proletarian characters on the ground can frequently form the essence of a higher reality, which can be argued in the case of Nikolai Ostrovsky's *How the Steel Was Tempered* (*Ispat* in Bengali). The hero of the fairy tale/folk tale also represents a higher reality, though that might not outwardly follow socialist realism. Clark's reading does not take into account the nuances of this doctrine of higher reality, and is reductive to the extent that it conflates Party structure and political hierarchy with the aesthetics of socialist realism.

Fig. 8: Front Cover of *Ispat* Vol. 1

Soviet Union embarks upon a heroic age; bravado, risk-taking, sacrifice, adventure and struggle against insurmountable odds come to characterise the staple material for Soviet literature. The corresponding elements from fairy tales and folk tales are increasingly emphasised, constituting models

fit for emulation. Such structures are crucially posited within the Ideological State Apparatus. The children's universe of fairy tales suddenly wake up to the higher call of the nation, and repeatedly come to the foreground of Soviet official myths. Here we see that the function of children's literature in Soviet Union becomes manifold. It acts as a repository of myths which are resourceful for the adult, mature world. But it is also a potently direct weapon for indoctrination. Ben Hellman notes:

On 17 February 1918, an article appeared in Pravda entitled “The Forgotten Weapon”. Only Three months had passed since the Bolshevik seizure of power, but the remoulding of society along socialist lines had already begun. Now it was the turn of children's literature. The keynote had been sounded by Lenin, who said that “the entire purpose of training, educating, and teaching young people should be to imbue them with communist ethics”. In “The Forgotten Weapon”, L. Kormchy, a minor children's writer, who had decided to join the winners, declared that children's literature was an indispensable ally in the process of moulding the new man. (294)

Fairy tales and other children's stories, in order to be attractive, must be accompanied by illustrations. The use of graphic art to further the cause of the Soviet system among the children has been a notable strategy from the beginning. Evgeny Steiner's *Stories for Little Comrades* studies the use of 'revolutionary' art to indoctrinate the children in the early decades (1920s and 1930s) of Soviet Union, and investigates the strange marriage of avant garde art with the totalitarian ideology during this time. Use of brilliant sketches, paintings, images, photographs and illustrations continued to adorn children's and adolescents' books in Soviet Union. There have also been attempts to process the history of the 1917 Bolshevik revolution into a graphic narrative meant for easy consumption of children and grown up readers alike, and *Rush Biplob Ki Ghotchilo (Russian Revolution: What Actually Happened)* is an interesting case in point. It came out in 1987. Again, a coffee table publication on the Russian Revolution (that came out in 1987, commemorating the 70th anniversary of the revolution) printed fully on glossy papers in royal size, titled *An Illustrated History of the Great October Socialist Revolution: 1917 Month by Month* has a chapter on Drawings by the children of 1917 with carefully chosen imagery from children's paintings. This is an indication of the lasting significance of children in the overall schema of Soviet publishing.

Fig. 9: *Rush Biplob Ki Ghotechilo*. History of 1917 in comics format

Fig. 10 (top right), 11, 12, 13: *An Illustrated History of the Great October Socialist Revolution: 1917 Month by Month* has a chapter titled “Drawings by the children of 1917”

Utpal Dutt's 1976 play "Lenin Kothay?" ("Where is Lenin?"), also performed as a popular *jatra*, was a gripping political thriller based on the months immediately preceding October 1917. Dutt inserts a sequence where Lenin, then absconding in Razliv, has a storytelling session with three peasant children (194). Again, the significance of children is asserted, when in the midst of political crises, Lenin spares his valuable time for interaction with children. Later when police conducts a raid, Lenin's life is dramatically saved by a child. More importantly, here in Dutt's play Lenin and the children represent a conventional, deep-rooted dyad that informs Soviet literature in a massive way, adult fictions and children's books alike. It is nothing short of a Soviet ritual, a certain rite of passage, as Katerina Clark argues in her book: it is the **spontaneity/consciousness** dialectic (22), a dyadic structure that forms the nucleus of Soviet myth of subjectivity. In the above example of Dutt's play, children represent *stixijnost'* or spontaneity, whereas Lenin represents *soznatel'nost'* or consciousness. However, this dyad should not be thought of in terms of a Bakhtinian dialogic structure. At best, it can be called pseudo-dialogic, because the outcome of this dialogue is fixed, and in many respects, the conversation between spontaneity and consciousness resembles ventriloquism, as consciousness is slated to win and eventually exert its control over spontaneity.

Fig.14: *An Illustrated History of the Great October Socialist Revolution: 1917 Month by Month* provides images of Razliv where Lenin absconded

Interestingly, this duality is closer to Bengal's very own *prakṛti-puruṣa* dualism from Sankhya philosophy than we would care to think. Clark observes that the “Russian word for spontaneity, *stixijnost'*, is formed from the root *stixija*, meaning 'the elements’” (110). The *stixijnost'-soznatel'nost'* dualism is therefore a binary opposition of matter and consciousness, very much like Bengal's own *prakṛti-puruṣa* dualism. However, the Sankhya school of philosophy is tragically aware of the overwhelming power of the elemental forces of nature over consciousness, which is represented by the standing Kali atop a lying Shiva, or a Krishna holding the feet of Radha, as I discussed in the JBS literature issue (Vol.3, No.1, 2014). In the Soviet paradigm, the opposite is the case. Here, the elemental forces of nature are meant to be triumphantly harnessed by consciousness. Sankhya's tragic awareness gave birth to the Buddhist notion of Moksha, where consciousness is freed from the confines of materiality. The Soviet triumphal dyad of the mastery of consciousness over spontaneity gave birth to the social realist notion of the *positive hero*, the most popular example of which is probably Pavel Korchagin from *How the Steel Was Tempered*. In Bengali, this novel by Nikolai Ostrovsky has been translated as *Ispat* (Steel), and has been immensely popular with the adolescent readers. Here we find a prototypical template where the hero's journey from spontaneity to consciousness is mapped, and the Soviet version of history is enacted within the microcosm of the textual universe.

Fig. 15: The back cover of *Ispat* Vol. 2

Clark calls Ostrovsky's novel “one of the all time classics of Socialist Realism” (131). The back cover of the Bengali edition declared that the book has been translated into 48 languages and published in 42 countries. In Soviet Union 495 editions of the text have appeared, and a total of 1.5 crore copies have been sold; further, it topped the list of the most loved novels, as voted by the Komsomol (Young Communists' League was called Komsomol) members. Ostrovsky's novel celebrates Komsomol, an organization that was set up on 29 October 1918, one year after the revolution. Komsomol was a compulsory all Russia organization. Membership was open to everybody from the age of 14 years to 28 years, and one needed to be a serious black sheep to be out of it.

Ostrovsky's novel was serially published in *Molodaya Gvardiya*, the Komsomol journal. The first part was published in 1932, and the second part in 1934. It was an autobiographical novel, and Pavel Korchagin is Ostrovsky himself. Korchagin as a child represents the raw, untamed force of nature, that is, spontaneity. As he grows up, he comes into contact with communist ideology. He gets to learn about the true path of Bolshevism under the tutelage of various mentors in different phases of his life as he embarks on his journey towards consciousness. This novel's success has a number of reasons. Both Ostrovsky as well as his novel's hero Korchagin are proletarian, and in a way they depict the successful march of the revolution itself. Clark finds in this novel “defining aspect of high Stalinist political culture”; it is a novel “of the Civil War ethos, of struggle, heroism, and 'Bolshevik Will', but above all, it provided what the age demanded – an entire heroic biography to function as an example” (131-2). Clark notes that “Korchagin is *the* positive hero of Soviet literature, *the* model figure for the Soviet people to emulate. ... it is his role to resolve symbolically that problematical dialectic between the forces of 'spontaneity' and those of 'consciousness’” (132-3). However, the tragic ending of the novel is given a miss by Clark while discussing about its favourable reception among readers. Revolution devours its children, as any history of revolutionary turmoil would testify.

Bengalis know this, and the popularity of *Ispat* might stem from the fact that not only it offered an authentic experience of an actual revolution that shook the world (which the reader could vicariously feel), but it also showed the tremendous price that such a revolution exacts and extracts from its followers. It must have struck a cord with the Bengali readers of twentieth century, who were no strangers to bloodshed, loss of lives and turbulent times.

One striking feature of such Soviet socialist realist narratives is that they appropriate the cultural ambience of folk and fairy tales, as we have already observed. The protagonist is very often like a *bogatyr* (knight) from a *bylina* (heroic poem), and the King that this bogatyr serves is the Soviet State, Lenin and Stalin themselves. Further, the obstacles in the path of revolution remind of the monsters that a hero must fight and defeat. In Soviet children's fairy tales, specific political correlations are made, where the fairy tale's protagonist resembles a Soviet hero, the magic helper is reminiscent of a Soviet mentor, and the story's happy ending relates to the “radiant future” of the classless paradise; Soviet fairy tales are thus consistently full of political motifs, as the foreword of *Politicised Magic* by Marina Balina et al points out (x), and notes that “the Soviets appropriated the fairy tale paradigm wholesale for propagandist purposes” (xii).

Fig. 16: The Parenting manual *Chelemeye Manush Kora Proshonghe* opens with distinct nationalist overtones

As the Children were fed with a regular diet of fairy tales with a determined agenda, rearing children was promoted to a level of science at par with scientific Marxism. The parenting manual *Chelemeye Manush Kora Proshonghe* (the title can be translated as “About Rearing the Kids”, though

the English version was rather seriously titled “Dialogues on Education”) is a case in point. It is anonymously written (which indicates that it was produced by the Soviet state itself), and we only have the name of the Bengali translator. This is a manual meant for parents, and it is striking how traditional, paternalistic, nationalistic and Russian this book is. The occasional socialist emphasis merges seamlessly with the values of tradition. The book opens with a series of paintings done by Russian children, and a brief write up exhorts the parents and children alike to feel proud about the past arts and crafts of one's own people, to be worthy of that past, and to preserve everything that was best in that past.

Further, this book declares: “The need of fish – water, the need of bird – sky, the need of animal – forests, mountains. And the need of human is motherland” (158). Here we find a distinct presence of nationalism which is organically extrapolated. Elsewhere, the manual proclaims: “The book written for children should have a positive hero, so that the kids can accept him as their ideal” (167). Fairy tales are specifically emphasised as a training process; for example, a girl child can learn a lot from the story of Cinderella. The hint is obvious: Cinderella used to do all the works of household, while her hard labour made her appear even more beautiful. Here she represents proletarian spirit that should welcome hard work, and the happy ending of the story correlates to the teleological design of Soviet communism. But more importantly, the story is liked by a girl child named Yulia in this anecdote recorded in *Chelemeye Manush Kora Proshonge* because “everything is logical and just” in this story of Cinderella (142). The political use of the Cinderella myth has been repeatedly observed on the celluloid in Soviet Union, as Balina's *Politicised Magic* notes: “The modern Cinderella continues to toil and to toilette ... in such celluloid fantasies as the Stalinist *Radiant Path* (*Svetlyi put'*, 1940, Grigory Alexandrov), the Stagnation-era blockbuster *Moscow Doesn't Believe in Tears* (*Moskva slezam ne verit*, 1979, Vladimir Menshov)” (ix-x).

In a conventional celebration of gender stereotypes, girls are trained into domestic labour by their grandmothers and mothers in *Chelemeye Manush Kora Proshonge* (142-3), while boys are trained to become rough and tough by their fathers (46). While discussing the case study of the Nikitin family, the father's statement is approvingly recorded where he says: “to avoid the indulgence, timidity and the conditioning of feminine protectiveness, the child also needs the language of men” (46). This is the traditional, patriarchal Russia, a Russia that is known to be strong, where gender stereotypes are deeply

ingrained. We may remember that Soviet Union never had any woman as the head of state, and upper strata of Soviet society did not have many women, in spite of being one of the first countries of the west to accord voting rights to women. It is this Russian nation, male and paternalistic, a veteran of many tough winters, which perpetuates itself in the pages of this manual.

One major feature of the underlying Russian nationalism that informs Soviet culture is that it often tends to affirm the comfortable certainties of gender stereotypes, instead of challenging and deconstructing them in the vein of western liberalism. In order to ensure maximum productivity from its citizens, the Soviet state needed its women to be as motherly as possible, while the men needed to be paternal in an exemplary way. The children are the elemental forces of nature, they stand for a spontaneity that is malleable, and must be shaped according to the dominant consciousness. *Chelemeye Manush Kora Proshonge* announces that the speciality of a child's character is that it is flexible, incredibly flexible (255). Clearly, the children are the soft raw materials who will be conditioned to grow up into pillars of strength to the Russian nation. And for this purpose, the renowned nineteenth century Russian educationist, Konstantin Ushinsky is freely quoted and pressed to service in *Chelemeye Manush Kora Proshonge*; for example, it is asserted through Ushinsky's statement that imparting knowledge to children and making their intelligence flourish are not sufficient, because children must learn to thirst to undertake labour for people's welfare (9). The Soviet state valued hard work, because it was built upon hard, superhuman labour. So it wanted to instil that value among the children.

A boy needs to know about the real handsomeness of men, that consists of “intelligence, strength and generosity”, as *Chelemeye Manush Kora Proshonge* observes (372). The parents are told: “your son will one day have to be a man, will have to be that person who in ancient times used to be called the stronger component of humankind, and even the worthiest part of the nation” (380). The patriarchal language of traditional Russia is unmistakeable. This book, published in 1987 encapsulates the essence of an old Russia that has withstood the vagaries of time: it used to be tsarist, then it was Stalinist, and it was now witnessing Gorbachev. The lessons from the ancient times were reissued time and again in the interest of the Russian regime. And nowhere else such lessons are imparted with such a degree of efficacy as in the fairy tales. The foreword to *Politicized Magic* by Marina Balina et al observes:

[T]hese works blatantly counter Vladimir Nabokov's apodictic assertion that 'literature is not a dog carrying message in its teeth'. Indeed, their messages appear in oversized italics and rely on the hermeneutical drumbeat of emphatic iteration (repetition, conveniently, being a cardinal feature of fairy tales). It is no coincidence that the premier Soviet directors of fairy-tale screen adaptations, Alexander Ptushko and Alexander Rou, thrived during Stalinism – an era dominated by the brutally utopian slogan: 'We were born to make fairy tales come true'. (x)

Katerina Clark points out that Soviet Union under Stalin “focused on the primordial attachments of kinship and protected them as the dominant symbol for social allegiance. Soviet society's leaders became 'fathers' (with Stalin as the patriarch); the national heroes, model 'sons'; the state, a 'family'” (114). We may notice that this familial feature singularly characterises the formation of nationalist discourse in most parts of the world where the organic ties of kinship are evoked to press the citizen to the service of the nation, as nation becomes identifiable with immediate kinship and familial bond. The call of the socialist fatherland during the time of Stalin has distinct echoes of nationalism. But what is more important is that across the decades, the latent nationalist character of the Soviet Russian propaganda literature remained unchanged. In *Ispat* too, Pavel Korchagin forms a community with the fellow believers in communism, that has organic kinship as its model of cohesion. Every mentor is a substitute father, and every trainee a son. The trainee gradually attains maturity and becomes a father figure himself, ready to inspire others and leave behind a legacy, which is the final destiny of Pavel Korchagin.

Korchagin is the archetypical positive hero, and it is quite interesting to note that the positive hero has been a part of the traditional Russian narrative. Particularly within nineteenth century realist texts, the positive hero looms large, according to Clark, who points out:

However, the positive hero has always played a role in the greater tradition of Russian literature (consider, for example, the heroes of Dostoevsky). This reflects the greater moral fervor to be found in modern Russian literature than in the West. Since the mid-nineteenth century, Russian critics have joined Russian writers setting out two tasks for literature that, although found in Western literature, have certainly not characterized it for roughly the past hundred years. These tasks were, first, to draw 'typical' characters – characters who were not so much individuals

as representatives of commonly found social types through which the writer was to present a critique of Russian life – and, second, to set forth models of behavior who might, by their example, show the way out of Russia's social ills.” (46)

Though we are discussing Soviet children's and adolescents' literature, some Kolkata publications should also be taken into consideration here. In all likelihood some of the first Soviet books were printed and published from Kolkata (we have already seen one example), probably because of the adverse logistics involved in a mass import, and given that the political climate was hostile to the communists in Bengal during the early 1950s. However, as more and more Soviet books started appearing directly from Soviet Union, the need for Kolkata reprints of Soviet books would not arise until the fall of 1991, following which some popular Soviet books again would be printed from Kolkata (John Reed's *Duniya Knapano Dosh Din* is a prime example of CPM-controlled National Book Agency's venture into reprints of Soviet classics in the post-Soviet era). The publications that we are concerned with here are the specific texts which were inspired and influenced by the Soviet ideological machinery, but were works composed by Bengali authors, published from Kolkata, not straightforward translations as such, but very much operating within the generic Soviet paradigms. Here I intend to discuss one work of fiction by Dineshchandra Chattopadhyay, *Duronto Eagle* and a non-fictional propaganda work centred on Soviet Children by Shyamal Chakraborty, *Shishutirthe Shishura* as type studies. We shall see that both of these two texts have soviet templates as their model.

Fig. 17: *Shishutirthe Shishura*

Fig. 18: *Duronto Eagle*

Chakraborty's text (1986, published by National Book Agency, CPM's publishing wing) comes within a long line of celebratory works which promote Soviet Union by making the Soviet children its brand ambassadors. Chakraborty, a minister in the CPM-led WB government and one of the top leaders of the party, went to Soviet Union for medical treatment and lived in a sanatorium near Yalta by the black sea, and he went to visit Artek, the most famous Pioneer (the advanced group of Soviet boys and girls who were brought together in a scout-like formation) camp of Soviet Union, established in 1925. Jawaharlal Nehru himself made a visit to Artek in 1955, and Artek continued to be the prized poster of Soviet propaganda focused on children. A description of Artek opens a monograph on Soviet children published by Progress Publishers in Bengali in 1989, which is authored by a pro-Soviet Indian writer, Jai Prakash Bharti. This Bengali translation came after Chakraborty's memoir was published, but both of them open with a rather tempting description of the breathtaking scenic beauty of this place in

Fig. 19: Jai Prakash Bharti's *Soviet Shishujogot*

Crimea. The descriptions of the geography and history of the seaside town of Hurzuf (where Artek is situated) given by Chakraborty and Bharti are very similar, and it rouses a suspicion that both of them are probably copying from the Soviet propaganda handed down to them, since they are speaking in one voice in spite of being separated from each other by language and time (in all likelihood Bharti did not read Bengali and he could not anyway read Chakraborty who wrote his memoir prior to Bharti's travels in Soviet Union).

The Soviet propaganda machine insisted that the only privileged classes of Soviet Union were its children, and both Chakraborty and Bharti make it a point to begin their respective texts with this exhortation, while highlighting the adage of Lenin: the best things are meant for the children. Both Chakraborty and Bharti fondly describe the myth of the bear mountain (Ayu-Dag) near the Artek camp in almost similar language. The standard pacifism of the Brezhnev era (stemming from the Soviet curtailing of Defence budget) utilised and mobilised the children to bring forth the message of world peace, and both Chakraborty and Bharti devote lengthy attentions to the pacifist movement launched internationally by the Artek Pioneers. In addition, Bharti also takes the name of Nehru in support of the Soviet agenda for world peace, while both Chakraborty and Bharti are calling for greater cooperation and contact between the children of Soviet Union and India. The facilities in the Artek camp are specially advertised in both the works, with an emphasis on the free services that the children enjoy there, contrasting it with the standard capitalist state's lack of welfare policies. The descriptions are indeed tantalisingly attractive, and bear testimony to the psychological effect of Soviet propaganda aimed at the children and adults alike, helping the spontaneous segments of the populace attain the nirvana of consciousness. And this was not mere propaganda, these writers genuinely believed in what they propagated. Chakraborty's book is fondly dedicated to his small daughter, Ushasie (who is a film and television actress of Kolkata today).

Dinesh Chattopadhyay the left-leaning publisher-writer was renowned as the founder editor and publisher of *Kishor Bharoti*, a monthly magazine in Bengali meant for teenagers. He wrote exclusively for adolescent readers. His novel *Duronto Eagle* is set in the Pamirs, reputed to be the roof of the world. The writer recognises Georgii Tushkan's *The Hunter of the Pamirs* as one of the influences on him in the foreword, but if we study both the texts side by side, Chattopadhyay's novel is revealed to be actually a direct translation of Tushkan's text, with some improvisations thrown in, the most notable of

which is the introduction of a Bengali communist character, Gora, who is not there in Tushkan's novel. Gora acts as Jura's mentor, and represents the consciousness to Jura's spontaneity. Barring this innovation, obviously aimed at the Bengali readers, this book is actually an unacknowledged translation of Tushkan's text. But Chattopadhyay claims authorship of *Duronto Eagle*, the status of which is not given as a translated work. Further, the blurb of the book proudly records some of the praise that Chattopadhyay received for the book, which announce the book to be an epic (review of the Bengali daily *Aajkal*), to be both an epic and a timeless classic (Manish Ghatak's review), which disturbingly suggest that these reviewers probably were not aware that it was not an original work and almost a verbatim copy of Georgii Tushkan's novel.

Georgii Tushkan's novel (full title of which is *The Hunter of the Pamirs: A Novel of Adventure in Soviet Central Asia*) followed the Soviet paradigm of the positive hero. Jura (all the character names remain unchanged in Chattopadhyay's book) is the protagonist whose journey from spontaneity to consciousness is depicted in the progression of the text. Living in a remote village of the Pamirs, Jura, his uncle Kuchak and his beloved Zeineb constitute the main troika of this novel who are uprooted from their safe hamlet and now have to undertake a journey across the hostile terrains of the Pamirs in the midst of the vortex of Basmachi rebellion during the early 1920s.

The Islamic character of Soviet Central Asia has variously influenced Soviet policies. Socialism was once identified with Islam in Soviet Union, and that was a geopolitical strategy aimed at central Asia. Sometimes such strategies extended to Soviet foreign policy. The central Asian fictions published from the Soviet Union in Bengali (Chingis Aitmatov's novels, for example) might have been intended to impart a closeness to Muslim Bangladesh, one can suspect. It is difficult to say if the usual proportion of such central Asian books in English translation was exceeded by the quantity of such books translated into Bengali, in the absence of official data. Nevertheless, stories with Muslim colour might have been endearing to the people in Bangladesh, given that the literature produced in West Bengal, though eagerly consumed by the Bangladeshi readers, very rarely had any Muslim character, or Islamic background. The 1986 collection of fairy tales, *Kon Se Desher Kon Sagorer Pare* has a few stories set in the backdrop of Muslim culture (written by Russian writers, though). Such stories while being generally popular in West Bengal (where the Muslim component would not disturb the process of readers' reception) they might have generated special enthusiasm in the eastern side, which was by this

time declared as Islamic republic by President Ershad, and Soviet Union must have taken note of that. So in this collection, Alexander Kuprin's "Kismet" is set in some faraway Muslim land which is not central Asia, as the story has a lot of the seashore and sea voyage, and also a Badshah. A Muslim merchant is the protagonist in this story. Another story of Lev Tolstoy titled "Nyaybicharok" (Judge) is set in Algeria. Lermontov's "Ashik Kerib", a Turkish fairy tale set in the Caucasus is also a part of this collection.

It is evident from the Soviet anthologies of fairy tales in translation that the Soviet system preferred the term 'folk tales' over fairy tales, for reasons obvious. While strongly discouraging supernatural stories (Soviet literature were distinguished by a total absence of ghost stories), the soft and aerial 'fairy' might have been discarded in favour of a sturdy, proletarian 'folk' (at least in all English and foreign language translations the word fairy has been either discouraged or outright manipulated; we shall observe the latter in Gorky's *Italyr Rupkotha*). Fairy tales in fact suffered severe castigations and onslaughts in the aftermath of the revolution during the 1920s, only to be reinstated to a status of usefulness in the mid-1930s, a process that Marina Balina chronicles in *Politicized Magic* while discussing the relation between fairy tales and socialist realism. She informs that a polemical text titled *We Are Against the Fairy Tale*, collectively authored by leading Soviet ideologues working in the field of children's education appeared in 1928, and then Balina further notes:

According to Felix J. Oinas, in the early 1920s "the belief that folklore reflected the ideology of the ruling classes gave rise to a strongly negative attitude toward it ... A special Children's Proletkult sought to eradicate folktales on the basis that they glorified tsars and tsareviches, corrupted and instigated sickly fantasies in children, developed the kulak attitude. And strengthened bourgeois ideals". Among the "enemies" of the fairy tale was the powerful Nadezhda Krupskaya, Lenin's widow, as well as a leading authority on education and library science in the new Soviet state. In 1924 Krupskaya (then the chair of the Central Committee on Political Education, or Glavpolitprosvet) was instrumental in putting together an influential manual that led to the exclusion of fairy tales from library shelves. Four years later she launched a campaign against Korney Chukovsky's literary fairy tales with an article in the leading governmental newspaper *Pravda* titled "On Crocodile", denouncing his famous fairy tale as "bourgeois nonsense" (*burzhuaznaia mut*). (106)

In the same breath, Balina observes: “it was considered 'bourgeois' by its very nature. Fairy-tale creatures such as magic, fantasy, animism, and anthropomorphism – all the devices that compose the essence of the genre – were condemned as 'idealism'” (107). Fairy tales continued to remain in the official blacklist of Soviet ideology for quite some time. And then, the story of the rehabilitation of fairy tales becomes equally interesting. While Balina gives a detailed account of that process, she does not ponder over the change in nomenclature, which suggests a tension that underlies the return of fairy tales as folk tales. This is a preference in nomenclature that remains till the end of Soviet Union, and they always preferred the term Folk over Fairy. Almost the fairy tale books which we have received in Bengali from Soviet Union carefully avoid the term fairy tale in their titles. They are not called *Rupkotha*, the conventional word for fairy tale in Bengali, and instead are called *Upokotha*, a vague neologism that stands for folk tales (folk tale should more properly be translated as *Lokokotha*).

Probably the term *lokokotha* was deliberately avoided to ward off suspicions from apolitical readers who might not want a political treatise in disguise while buying books for their children, given that such anthologies were aimed at a large readership, far beyond the politically initiated. The word *upokotha* resonates and rhymes with *rupkotha* and the former can be easily mistaken for the latter by a reader who might simply overlook the difference. This may be an interesting case of expediency in Bengali translations of Soviet books. Whatever might have been the intricacies, the minute changes in nomenclature deserve our attention as they expose the psychopolitics of words where this nomenclature is at work. Historians have generally agreed that Stalin shared a bitter history of enmity with Krupskaya. Balina does not take that into account, but it nonetheless might have acted as a factor in Stalin's whole hearted support behind the Soviet Union's official restoration of fairy tales, which was inaugurated by Gorky in 1934.

The task of revitalization fell to Maxim Gorky, the father of socialist realism, whose speech at the first Soviet Writers' Congress in August 1934 signaled the fairy tale's ideological rehabilitation. Of this famous opening speech, Oinas has written, “Gor'kii's insistence that folklore belonged, first of all, to working people had far-reaching implications. As if by magic, it opened the eyes of the party leaders to the possibilities that folklore would have for the advancement of communism. And from that time on, we can follow the conscious use of folklore for social and political use”. In his speech, Gorky pronounced such folktale characters

as Vasilisa the Wise and “the ironically lucky Ivan the Simple” to be meritorious individuals and praised both folklore and the folktale for their lack of pessimism and their participation in the struggle for “the renovation of life”. ... Samuil Marshak, who delivered his speech immediately after Gorky's, made the next important statement. The topic of his presentation was children's literature, and the importance given to this subject indicates the special significance the party assigned to the literature of the new generation. Marshak's speech outlined key moments in the development of children's literature. While Gorky carefully confined himself to general statements about folklore, Marshak did not hesitate to use the word “fairy tale” (*skazka*). In the Soviet Union, he insisted, “We have everything necessary for the development of an outstanding and unique literature for children, for the creation of such fairy tales ... as never existed anywhere else.” (Balina *Politicizing Magic* 107-8)

Marina Balina does not recognise the crucial politics played in this dichotomy of fairy tale and folk tale, and mentions it *en passe*. Further, *skazka* literally is Russian for tale, not fairy tale. In the opinion of the present researcher, this binary of fairy and folk deserves our attention. We realise that fairy tale, which was given a bad name and suppressed during the 1920s, which returned during the 1930s in a born again avatar, had to undergo a certain realignment of structure and nomenclature, as the emphasis on folk tale suggests. An interesting case study in this regard will be Maxim Gorky's book, translated into Bengali as *Italyr Rupkotha* (Fairy Tales of Italy), though the English name of the book on the copyright page is simply (and correctly, as it is internationally known) given as *Tales of Italy*.

Fig. 20 & 21: Front cover and content of *Italyr Rupkotha*. Note that the title of the very first story is “Strike”

The use of the term *rupkotha* is an interesting case of appropriation of this genre for political purpose, utilising the potency, appeal and innocence of the term, thus making inroads into the bookshelves of young readers and their parents alike. This is an interesting case of manipulating tradition, as the stories are those of contemporary Italian working people (composed during Gorky's sojourn in Italy between 1906 and 1913), and have nothing to do with the form and content of conventional fairy tales. This is a supreme example of political restructuring of a genre, and what is most interesting to observe in this case is that Gorky's policy regarding fairy/folk tale, declared in 1934, continues to have a far-reaching implication in the Soviet strategy governing the Bengali translations, where the word *rupkotha* is cunningly surcharged into the Bengali title in 1984, ensuring a revolutionary transaction of proletarian values to be instilled in the mind of the reader who approaches the book with innocent expectations. This initiative adds an entirely new dimension to the political appropriation of the genre of fairy tales. Conventional fairy tales have been read as an allegory of the Soviet version of history and the progression of the proletariat, but what we find here is a complete redefining of the genre, where contemporary tales involving workers which have no resemblance to the standard and traditional pattern of fairy tales are given the name *rupkotha* specifically in the Bengali translation (the English version continues to be issued under the non-ambitious title *Tales of Italy*).

The Bengali book opens with a quotation from Hans Anderson which justifies the use of the term *rupkotha*: “No finer fairy tales are there than what is written by Life itself”. However, the English translation gives this quotation in a different way: “There are no tales finer than those created by life itself”.² Mykhailo Kotsiubynsky, the noted Ukrainian writer's praise of the book is also given in the Bengali translation: “Thanks for the Fairy Tales. So much of love is there for mankind, so much of awareness for life and so much of feeling for nature. A wonderful, sun-bathed book”. Given that Kotsiubynsky died in 1913, he is out of the political agenda of the Soviet design regarding fairy tales, let alone the strategy governing the Bengali translation of these stories. However, the trajectory from tale to fairy tale is foreshadowed by Gorky's statement where he observed: “I have called these scenes Tales, because both the landscape of Italy and the customs of its people, indeed their entire way of life, is (sic) so different from Russia that to the ordinary Russian reader they might indeed seem like tales.”³ Some of these stories are set in urban, metropolitan Italy of Genoa and Naples, while some of them take place in the remote mountains and lakes of Italy, but every story is weaved in the backdrop of contemporary times and has the toiling Italian people as its characters.

The Soviet use of the genre of fairy tales to highlight the toiling masses sometimes involved a minor realignment of the stories where the protagonist's class status was suitably altered, or the class enemy suitably vilified in order to match the political agenda. *Rushdesher Upokotha* is a case in point. Interestingly, these are actual, traditional fairy tales, unlike Gorky's *Tales of Italy*, and therefore the nomenclature of *upokotha* (literally, sub-tales, but this is what has always been used in the Bengali translations of Russian, Ukrainian and other Soviet fairy tales) becomes significant. The English title of the book is given as *Russian Folk Tales*. The penultimate story is that of Alyosha Popovich. As Soumyendra Sikdar's study points out, Alyosha Popovich was a boyar, i.e. a feudal lord, whereas Ilya Muromets was from the peasant stock (14). Sikdar does not note the problematic nature of class status of a boyar hero within the Soviet transmission of fairy tales, though. But the free mixing of classes in the world of fairy tales is a direct anathema to the class struggle version of history, and therefore Soviet storytelling tried to realign the narrative. It's easier to do so for the Bengali readers (and other non-Soviet ones), because they are not already familiar with the narratives.

Fig. 22: Front cover of *Rushdesher Upokotha*

The boyars stood second highest in the royal hierarchy, only next to the prince. Now, *Rushdesher Upokotha* simply presents Alyosha as a bogatyr, or knight-errant, which he indeed was in the legends, and shows him as a son of a village priest, which he also was in the legends. But Alyosha attained aristocratic status, became a boyar, and that is erased from his tale that we find in this anthology. But, interestingly, the story on the equally famous bogatyr Dobrynya Nikitich shows Alyosha in a brief cameo, having negative characteristics, false accusing Dobrynya to be friends with the mythical serpent Zmey Gorynych, and thus making Dobrynya fight the serpent alone. Out of the three famous bogatyrs from the legends of the Kievan Rus, only Alyosha is singled out to play a minor villain in one of the stories. One can understand that the boyar status of Alyosha, though remains unspoken, nonetheless functions as an invisible subtext.

There are two collections of fairy tales from Ukraine that we have in Bengali translation. The 1954 text, which we have already mentioned earlier, *Ukrainiyo Upokotha*, was a slender volume of four stories, published from Kolkata under an arrangement with Foreign Language Publishing House, Moscow. The name of the original Soviet text is given as Ukrainskye Narodnye Skazki. No English title is given, but as per my knowledge of Russian, it would be Ukrainian Folk Tale. This is one of the first (probably the first) Soviet children's publications in Bengali, and this is the first time the word *upokotha* is coined to signify folk tales. But the 1988 text, the Russian name of which is also given as Ukrainskye Narodnye Skazki, and the English name as Ukrainian Folk Tales, is called *Ukrainer Lokokotha* in Bengali, and this is the lone instance where the proper translation of the term folk tale has been used in Soviet Bengali publications. The previous collection of Ukrainian fairy tales might have clashed with the new book if it was also called *upokotha*, and probably that was why the new edition was named *lokokotha*. Or, one can speculate that by 1988, Soviet publication stopped feeling any need for the vague neologism *upokotha* for the Bengali reader, by now under communist rule for 11 years, and came straight to the political point, in a folksy way. The 1988 collection as well as the 1954 one contain mostly animal fables, and stand in stark contrast with the Russian fairy tales, which though have their own dose of animal fables, but are predominated by tales of bravery of soldiers, bogatyrs and great heroes fighting with great monsters. The small domestic animals and domestic-like wild animals who predominate the Ukrainian collection might betray a Russian imperial design to show Ukraine as the perennial Malorossiia, Little Russia, the smallish land on the margin, having only small stories to tell involving small animals.

Fig. 23: *Ukrainer Upokotha* of 1988

Katerina Clark pinpoints the political use of fairy tales in Soviet Russia when she comments: “In order to describe *homo extraordinarius*, one needed more fabulous forms, such as fairy tales” (147). So the fairy tales connected the dreadful quotidian of Soviet citizen's life with the promised future of communism by their structural juxtaposition of hardship and victory, obstacles and happy ending, ordinary persons and extraordinary fantasies. The fairy tale characters like Khude Ivan boro buddhiman (Small Ivan the intelligent) and Sivka Burka Jaduka Ladka (Sivka Burka the Son of Magic) have been popular with generations of Bengali readers, and they represent this secret passage from a dreary existence to a dazzling life of enchantment. The immense popularity of the Soviet fairy tales in Bengali stems from this trait: they presented an escape from our drudgery, they represented an elusive reality that was forever out of our reach but tantalisingly close, as close as the printed book. In a way,

the socialist fatherland, the immense land of Russia became the land of fairy tales for the Bengali reader. The dreadfulness of the present times notwithstanding, they offered an escape into a wonderland, where men were brave, where the honest people won in the end, where the monsters were defeated and beautiful maidens became princesses. What Soviet socialism could not attain in reality, the same could be attained on the pages of the fairy tales. Moreover, the fairy tales, deeply conventional, offered the traditional values of Russia in a disseminable format for the international readers. The Bengali readers developed their Russophilia mainly from reading these texts. The fairy tales also symbolise a land of renewal, of reinvigoration, of rebirth, where a Cinderella-like transformation awaits the reader. The fairy tales, in short, stood for an ideal, it was the ideal of a promised land. The fairy tales stood for Soviet Union, which remained an ideal. However, fairy tales did not always stand for an unrealized ideal, let alone a remote and abstract version of Soviet history. The fairy tales were a consistent source of inspiration for the projects of reality (including the writing of socialist realist novels). And sometimes they became reality. Clark notes that “in *Continuation of a Legend* fairy tale does become reality: one of the workers tells a local folktale in which the Yenisey and Angara rivers are united – as in reality they are in the Irkutsk project (229).

In the age of science and technology, science fictions become a major genre all over the world. They share some common features with fairy tales. Both are imaginative, and depict incredible feats of men and women. Magical and supernatural creatures show a strong similarity with the fantastical beings of science fictions. The enchanted world of a *bogatyr* is very often paralleled by the alternative world of the protagonist of science fiction. Alexander Belyaev's *Ubhochor Manush* (*The Amphibious Man/The Amphibian*) is a case in point. This 1928 novel was made into a massive Soviet blockbuster movie in 1962, directed by Vladimir Chebotaryov.⁴ The novel seems like a fairy tale of science, so does the movie (indeed, the initial sequence of the Russian movie of 1962 shows an incredulous Pedro Zurita dismissing the story of the sea devil as *skazki*, or tale).⁵ *Ubhochor Manush* has enjoyed a lasting popularity among Bengali readers. It has been made into radio plays in Bengali a number of times, and in a few of them the story's ending is altered to show a happy conclusion, probably on audience's demand. The novel's plot has fantasy, it has romance, it has melodrama and it has tragedy. Dr Salvator is a maverick scientist and medical doctor based in Buenos Aires, Argentina. His foster son, Ichthyander has been operated by him and given shark gills so that Ichthyander can breathe underwater. Ichthyander is mistaken as the sea devil by the local fishermen. He rides on a dolphin and wanders

through the bay. Following a chance encounter, Ichthyander falls in love with Guttere, a beautiful young maiden who in turn is pursued by Zurita, the villain of the story who also tries to get Ichthyander trapped and imprisoned for his own selfish motives (Zurita is a merchant of pearls and he wants to use Ichthyander as an underwater diver). Ichthyander, now madly in love with Guttere, starts spending increasingly more time on land, which becomes detrimental for his health to the point where he finally has to forsake his amphibious self and Guttere herself, and spend the rest of his life in water. At the end of the story, he travels to a faraway place under instructions from Salvator. The sad ending of the novel is particularly striking, as it subtly undercuts the triumphant socialist realist dogma without going against it in an obvious way. Salvator is shown to be persecuted by a dogmatically religious administration for his acts against God (like creating the amphibious man), which is a typically communistic depiction of Christianity as regressive. This is a sentimental novel, and it also emphasises the high Stalinist paradigm of life-altering role of science and technology. Ichthyander, (fish-man as per the Greek etymology) stands for the elements of nature shaped by the forces of science which are identifiable with revolutionary consciousness epitomised by Surgeon Salvator. The final tragedy in the life of Ichthyander can be reconciled with socialist framework citing the evil of capitalism, as the events were taking place in a capitalist country with strong Catholic (shorthand for feudal) bias.

Fig. 24 & 25: Front cover of *Ubhohor Manush* and an illustration from the book depicting Ichthyander and Guttere

Love in this novel causes a relapse into untamed and raw materiality. Love causes indiscipline and leads to life-threatening risk. Soviet love stories have been sometimes derided by western critics as “boy gets tractor” narratives (Clark 209), where the protagonist instead of getting the love of his life, ends up getting a tractor or something equivalent and contributes to the forward march of socialism. Reproduction is suppressed in favour of production, as one may quip. Ichthyander does not get the girl he loves, but he is promised with the final triumph of science instead. In fact he is punished for his love in the novel, and it is only by forsaking the spontaneity of love and returning to the dominant authority of Salvator (i.e. consciousness) that he can be salvaged. Further, Ichthyander's love for Guttere has a forbidden aspect too (unknown to both of them), as Guttere is his half-sister. Baltasar the professional diver working for Zurita is the father of both of them. Ichthyander was an infant when his mother died and he was given to Salvator for treatment by Cristo, Baltasar's elder brother. Salvator later told Cristo that the baby has died. However, Salvator lied, and Ichthyander was successfully operated only to be turned into the amphibious man. When Baltasar gets to know about it, he wants to get Ichthyander back, and there is a high emotional drama in the plot.

There is a covert critique of Stalin-era brutality of industrialisation in the snatching away of Ichthyander from his biological father, Baltasar. The novel in fact ends with a half-mad Baltasar calling out loudly to Ichthyander by the sea on stormy nights, and the separation of the father from the son for the sake of science can be read as a secret narrative of the human being's alienation from his immediate root, identity, nature, community and property caused by rapid industrialisation in the Soviet state. It is indeed sad that this popular fiction of multi-layered significations has not merited a detailed discussion from the critics who study Soviet literature.

The country and the city (Raymond Williams' eponymous study immediately coming to mind) exist as an interesting dyad within the Soviet children's literature, and the dynamics of this dyadic structure has changed across the Soviet period. For the period of Lenin and Stalin, rural world represented the natural element meant to be tamed. Villages stood for the raw materiality which needed to be moulded and shaped by consciousness. Struggle with nature was a recurrent motif. Man pitted against a hostile nature was a central Stalinist era image, as Katerina Clark points out (100). But this interrelationship changes with time, and by the late 1940s and early 1950s, the world of nature comes to suggest a haven and refuge from the vagaries of the world of men, the world of war, technology and

corruption. Now the village represented a pristine, prelapsarian Russia, that was not corrupt, that was not bureaucratic, and that was not unfree, and the city was its exact opposite. An interesting example of this evolution is Nikolai Dubov's *Shagortire* published in 1985. It has two novellas, “Nodir Buke Alor Mala” and “Shagortire”. “Nodir Buke Alor Mala” is a novella from 1952, published in English as *Lights on the River*. It was also made into a popular Soviet movie as the foreword to the Bengali translation informs (5). Dubov himself came from the working classes, and this novella (as well as “Shagortire”) celebrates the life of labour.

Fig. 26: Front cover of *Lights on the River* (1952), the novella translated as “Nodir Buke Alor Mala” included in the selection titled *Shagortire*

Fig. 27: Front cover of *Shagortire* (1985)

As “Nodir Buke Alor Mala” opens, Kostya, the protagonist, is presented to the reader as spontaneity incarnate. He studies in fifth standard in Kiev, is immature, and is not at all conscious of his responsibilities. He does not participate in Pioneer activities, takes an idle interest in movies and sports, and is far from the ideal boy. But his journey on a steamer from the city to the village along the river Dnieper is a beginning of a quest that will change him forever. This is a narrative where Kostya, the immature child protagonist turns into a mature adolescent boy ready to participate in the building of Soviet Union. It is a coming of age narrative, and that way it can be called a typical Stalinist novel, the paradigm of which continues in the post-Stalinist literature mostly unchanged, involving “a rite of passage by which the hero passes from a state of 'spontaneity' to one of 'consciousness' and thus achieves social integration” (Clark 226). This ritual of metamorphosis takes place in the midst of wonderful natural scenery of Polyanskaya. Clark notes that instead of the high Stalinist emphasis on urbanisation and industrialisation, the novels of 1950s, particularly the youth novels (and Dubov's novella can qualify as one; though Clark considers the genre to have been inaugurated only in 1956, which is four years after “Nodir Buke Alor Mala” was written; sadly, she does not take Dubov into consideration anywhere in her study) insisted on the redeeming qualities of rural life. Kostya's journey from the city to the village is also a passage from Stalinism to post-Stalinism, though it was written during the fag end of Stalinist period. This is how Clark delineates the evolution of the Soviet paradigm:

In the Stalinist novel, Moscow functioned as a place prefiguring the higher-order reality to come in Communism, while the provincial town, factory, construction site, or kolkhoz in which the novel was set was bound to be far behind Moscow on the path to perfection. In the youth novel, by contrast, Moscow (or Leningrad) functions as the “false” place, polluted by bureaucracy, careerism, insincerity, and other such “Stalinist” ills, whereas some place “far away from Moscow” (in the words of the title of Azhaev's Zhdanovist classic) and, preferably, dramatically less civilized than Moscow (or Leningrad) becomes the haven of Leninist ideals to which the hero is drawn. (227)

Kostya represents the frivolity of the city that is at odds with the seriousness of rural life that is epitomised in the character of his maternal uncle and mentor Yefim Kondratyevich, resident of Polyanskaya. Interestingly in Dubov's work the city stands for untrained, unconscious materiality

whereas remote Polyanskaya is the site of consciousness. The text celebrates physical labour, and emphasises on physical labour as the singular force that is restructuring a devastated nation in the aftermath of second world war, which stands as a recurrent motif, still fresh in recent memory. The child protagonist Kostya is an orphan who lost his father in the second world war. Further, Kostya's mentor and father figure Yefim Kondratyevich is himself a veteran of the war. The war anecdotes of bravery and strength recur in the narrative, as they play an important role in the rite of passage that Kostya undergoes. If the great war lurks in the background, then communism is foregrounded in this narrative. While communism as the distinct horizon is repeatedly pointed to, a technocratic, bureaucratic attitude to communism is repudiated by Dubov, who above all values organic unity between man and nature, and the sweaty, swarthy, earthen quality of communist labour. This novella thus foreshadows post-Stalinist aesthetics, and is an interesting case study in the transition of Soviet children's literature from Stalinism to post-Stalinism.

The second novella “Shagortire” (*The Boy at the Seashore/A Boy by the Sea*, a 1963 work) gives the volume its title, and was also made into a film. In this melancholy, slow narrative, there is a critique of the Soviet system where the child protagonist Sashuk meets an ex-convict who has served prison term for alleged subversion against the Soviet regime. The man is revealed to be innocent, and a victim of Stalin-era bureaucratic high-handedness. This is a text that came during the fag end of Khrushchev years, and it already shows some signs of transition to the Brezhnevist times in its (albeit critical) exhibition of consumerism. The journey to the sea follows the pattern of youth novels as we have already seen. The Stalinist socialist realist paradigm of the rite of passage is however sustained, and so is the spontaneity/consciousness dialectic. Sashuk represents spontaneity, whereas the ex-convict, Zorka, who is also a mentor figure, represents consciousness.

Dubov's book is published in Bengali in 1985, and in 1987 Raduga publishes Vsevolod NESTAIKO's *Dui Iyarer Joto Kando* (in English *Two Toreadors from Vasukovka Village*), also a Ukrainian text, and like Dubov's book, this book also has two novellas: “Ajob Adventure” (Strange Adventure) and “Ghori Niye Ghoraghuri” (Running after a Watch), but unlike *Shagortire*, the two novellas of *Dui Iyarer Joto Kando* are connected. They narrate events with the same set of protagonists, and the two novellas form a sequence. The Bengali translation of the second title is rather Shibramesque, as it uses a pun that would remind any Bengali reader the style of Shibram Chakraborty. In spite of all attempts

by the present researcher, the year of publication of the Russian original could not be ascertained. However, *Two Treaders from Vasyukivka* (spelling is differently given as Vasukovka, Vasiukovka, Vasyukovka and Vasyukivka) was made into an acclaimed Soviet Russian movie which won prizes in a few film festivals in 1968 and '69. It can be safely assumed that the text belongs to the early or mid 1960s. There is a distinctly Brezhnevite dimension of this text to which I shall come presently.

Fig. 28: *Dui Iyarer Joto Kando*

আজব
এডভেঞ্চার

Fig. 29: "Ajob Adventure"

ঘড়ি নিয়ে
ঘোরাঘুরি

Fig. 30: "Ghori Niye Ghoraghuri"

This period heralded prosperity in Soviet life, and this is a text that shows Soviet urban comfort and the glamour of city life of Kiev. The two protagonists, both of whom are students of fifth standard who get promoted to the sixth class during the narrative's progression, are called Java and Pavel. The text is full of humour. A major source of the comic discrepancy/incongruity that gives birth to laughter in the text can be detected in the tension between initiative and discipline, or planning and outcome. Clark notes that in 1952 a leading Soviet ideologue and writer Valentin Ovechkin in a brief sketch explored the dichotomy between initiative and discipline as one of the dominant tensions of the Soviet

system (214). Though Clark does not pay any attention to Nestaiko, nor does she realise the humorous potential of that tension between initiative and discipline, and limits herself solely to serious literature centred on that dichotomy, but we can safely state that this initiative/discipline duality informs the core of Nestaiko's strategy for eliciting humour in his text.

Interestingly, in Nestaiko's text, the city is reinstated to its glory, but not of a Stalinist kind. The city is more consumerist, the glamour of the film world is a recurrent motif and the main plot of the second novella revolves around the Kiev film world. A high voltage football game between Kiev and Moscow at the sports stadium acts as a pivot in the plot of “Ghori Niye Ghoraghuri”. Leisure sports on the banks of Dniepar are alluringly presented by Nestaiko. Among the teenager characters with whom Pavel and Java become friends in the city, there is also an outlaw, a marked man (“dagi” in Bengali) who, as Pavel and Java are told, has been jailed for shadowy activities and is now wanted by militia. As a plot device, it generates suspense in the search for the lost wristwatch which is the title theme in “Ghori Niye Ghoraghuri”. However, after a lot of adventure in the underground sewerage tunnel, it is finally revealed that it was a prank, and the boy referred to as “dagi” is a rather innocent lad from the neighbourhood named Vovka Ivanov. In this way, the innocence of the supposed outlaw is established, and the possibility of any actual subversion is annulled, just the way Dubov's “Shagortire” expels the possibility of any genuinely anti-Soviet act, showing the ex-convict to be an innocent victim of circumstances.

There is a certain glorification of the Kiev's underground tunnels in Nestaiko. The urban, nocturnal underground not only adds to the text's thrill, but also makes it multi-faceted, fit to be read against the grain as a covert celebration of the non-Soviet at the heart of Soviet rule. The depiction of the city is not merely Brezhnevist, it foreshadows Glasnost in a sense: the text has an openness to an extent that it has the charm of the forbidden. In the first novella, “Ajob Adventure” the main plot revolves around the Soviet culture of suspicion, where a certain character is suspected to be a foreign spy, and in the climax he is just revealed to be a person who caught fishes on the sly. Its 1987 publication coincides with the inauguration of Glasnost in USSR, and that may not be just a coincidence. The trajectory of the youth novels is reversed in Nestaiko's text: the journey now takes place from the village to the city. But this is not a Stalinist journey at all. Very significantly, the conventional **spontaneity/consciousness** dyad, dominant in all Soviet texts since the heydays of high

Stalinism shows signs of being deconstructed in *Nestaiko* for the first time. Pavel and Java remain as they are, topsy turvy and haphazard, with the only change that they become writers of their own stories in the end. The celebration of Cossack heritage is done by a bunch of children who claim the Cossack inheritance and taunt a rival group of children of the peasant stock. This is a deviation from the older Soviet paradigm, where the toiling peasants represent positive forces. In fact, in this text, the protagonists do not portray positive and ideal characters. They are truant, they tend to make a mess of everything, and yet they are favourably drawn and not the toppers of their class who go to pioneer camps. Further, the nationalist heritage of Ukraine is evoked in this celebration of the Dnieper- Cossacks, and also of the ancient legacy of the emperor Vladimir Monomakh of Kievan Rus. This is nothing less than a nationalist cultural revolution, and it shows strong signs of the official Soviet orthodoxies getting dismantled in favour of traditional Ukraine, the Vasukovka village being its cornerstone. The humorous episode of Kiev academicians coming to Vasukovka during the hunting season, and getting it all wrong in the act of hunting in the midst of the great marsh near the village can be read as an interesting allegory of Soviet discourse getting undercut by traditional Ukraine.

Thus we may diagnose a Soviet versus Russia conflict or a socialism versus nationalism dialectic working out of the pages of the books of Raduga and Progress, though these opposing currents mostly tended to overlap. But one may wonder what our reading should be of the third publishing house, Mir, that continued to operate even after the collapse of Soviet Union, unlike Raduga and Progress which stopped their operations in 1991. Mir (in Russian language the word can mean peace, world or village depending on the context) in fact continues to function to this day. It specialised (and it still does) in science and technology related publications. It too offered cheap price and excellent physical quality of books, which the Soviet books were known for. Mir was renowned for its popular science books in Bengali translation in the fields of physics, chemistry, biology etc. While such books catered to and were popular with students and general readers alike, almost no cultural study has yet been undertaken to analyse the political structure of Soviet popular science books, or how they have functioned as ISA, or their general role in fostering a sense of Russophilia or love for Soviet Union. However, a few observations can be made. These books circulated the Soviet grand narrative of materialist conception of history and the deterministic version of the world. They undercut the role played by genetics and promoted social conditioning as the determinant force in the creation of ideal subjects. Thus our study of the parenting manual earlier in this article sums up the spirit of Soviet

popular science books. They had a triumphant, upbeat, deterministic, teleological story of science to tell, and they did it in a captivating manner. The present researcher while in high school fell in love with the subject of animal physiology after reading the book *Physiology for Everyone*, a 1978 publication from Mir (the Bengali title was “Sharirtottwo Shobai Poro” the far I can remember).

Bengalis have variously responded to the fall of Soviet Union in 1991. It can be shown that Nabarun Bhattacharya's *Herbert* among other things is a response to the great fall of the USSR. Satyajit Ray's penultimate film *ShakhaProshakha* has a character, an educated Bengali middle class youth who is deeply pained by the fall of socialism in eastern Europe, and that captured the Bengali trauma caused by the counter-revolutionary turn of history. Utpal Dutt authored a book, *Protibiplob* that studied the trajectory of the fall of Soviet Union from its earliest days. The possibility of fall was already there, as Marx cautioned against the building of socialism in any backward economy with poorly developed democratic institutions, and it is identified by Dutt as the root cause of the collapse of Soviet Union.

Soviet Union's state-sponsored publishing industry continued to produce good quality children's literature, whatever may be its drawbacks. The children's books in the post-Soviet Russia are in a dismal state, as *Russian Children's Literature and Culture* by Marina Balina et al notes:

The state dispensed lavish funds on supporting children's literature and culture in the Soviet period, but when these subsidies ended with the crumbling of the Soviet system in 1991, the institutions of state-sponsored children's culture vanished, leaving the production and distribution of children's literature to the free publishing market.

The fact that children's literature is no longer a powerful institution is hard for most Russian parents to accept. Educators and literary critics are alarmed by the low intellectual quality of new books for children and periodically address this issue in the popular press and professional journals. (xv-xvi)

Fig. 31: An image from the “Soviet books in Bengali” blog

It is perhaps too early to say that the tremendous popularity, the lasting appeal of the Soviet books have withstood the test of time. But the innocent love expressed by the common readers at the “Soviet books in Bengali” blog is a testimony to the sustained charm that these books cast over multiple generations of Bengali reading public. It is noticed that there are sites who now poach books from this blog into their own domain to increase their popularity.

Fig 32: An image from a 'rival site' that allegedly poaches the ebooks uploaded by the original blog

The present researcher remembers that after he had internet connection at home for the first time in life (was a university student), the first google search that he did was on Vsevolod NESTAIKO. It was back in 2005, and NESTAIKO was still alive, though not a single English language resource existed on him in the internet. The wiki article was still not there. This has been our generation's level of lasting attachment to Soviet books. The present researcher opened and administered the first and probably only Orkut community of the Bengali and Indian lovers of Soviet books, named “We Love Soviet Books” back in 2005. Since then, there has been a proliferation of such nostalgic projects which celebrate the fond memories of Soviet books.

The Russo-Bengal connection is old, and it started when our revolutionary nationalists got in touch with Russia for possible help against the British. A detailed study of this connection has not been made yet. Studying the connection between Soviet Union and Bengal is beyond the scope of this article. The study of Soviet children's books in Bengali is a vast field. Who were the first interpreters, what was the history of the first publications? And how did it evolve? What was the publication history of the original texts in Russian? How were the books chosen for translation by the apparatchiks?

Fig 33: A screenshot of the extinct Orkut Community Page created by the present author, probably first of its kind. It gradually became inactive, as Facebook dislodged Orkut

We see that a number of the popular texts chosen for translation were already made into successful films (e.g. *Amphibian Man*, *Two Toreadors from Vasukovka*, *Boy by the Sea*, *Lights on the River*). Celluloid success was probably a factor behind the choice of these texts for getting translated. How many copies used to come, how they used to come, and who were the people in the undivided communist party who looked after the whole process, one wonders. What were the Soviet orders, what government notifications and minutes, and what policy adopted by the Soviet establishment declared the setting up and eventual expansion of the Bengali wing in the Foreign Language Publishing House? How did the Bengali readers at home receive these texts, what was social location of the readers of Soviet books, what was the contemporary readers' response and how do the nostalgic generations feel and reminisce about these

books today? There can be so many questions which we need to ask, and find their answers in the Bengali writings, and in the Russian archives housing Soviet era documents. It is a project that will involve many years of hardwork and combined effort of Bengali scholars, some of whom must know the Russian language. This article is a mere token of recognition of the vast potential of this field, and this is a humble inauguration of academic discussions into the Soviet Bengali books.

The role played by the Soviet books in perpetrating communist ideology should obviously be studied. But the nationalist undercurrent in Soviet Union, the trajectory of its evolution finally leading to the rise of nationalism in Putin's Russia today are also important topics for investigation, as a post-communist Bengal might have some lessons to learn from the Russian experience. Bengal's Communist stalls draped in red clothes during Durgapuja selling Soviet books were significant, because they represented the toddler steps of our communist politics under the guiding hand of Bengal's rooted cultural identity of Shakti worship (the colour of Shakti is also red). Soviet Union is gone, and communist rule in Bengal is gone too, but the historical connections between Bengal and Russia need to be studied in details. The present researcher is a keen observer of contemporary Russia. We need to study the rise of Putin in the context of the fourth political theory of Alexander Dugin. These are interesting developments that deserve our attention while we at *Journal of Bengali Studies* are working at a project committed to Bengali nationalism. We shall preserve our fascinations at the wide steppes, at the Dnieper, at the snow covered forests of White Russia. For all we know, Russia and Bengal may meet again at another turn of history.

Fig. 34: An image from Belarus, taken on 5 December 2012. Sourced from internet

Notes

1. Listen to the contemporary Russian national anthem adopted by Putin and the Soviet-era anthem that was adopted by Stalin respectively:

<<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AOAtz8xWM0w>>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x72w_69yS1A>.

(lyrics in Russian transliteration and English translation are given)

2. See <<http://www.amazon.com/Tales-Italy-Maxim-Gorky/dp/1589635272>>.

3. See <<http://www.amazon.com/Tales-Italy-Maxim-Gorky/dp/1589635272>>.

4. The wiki article says that the Russian movie had a total of 65 million ticket sales <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Amphibian_Man>.

5. Watch the 1962 movie with subtitles <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q1c4UEfAEjo>>.

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